

IMPROVEMENT OF THE METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN THE CONTEXT OF EDUCATION DIGITALIZATION

Barotova Marjona Shavkatovna

is a lecturer at the Department of Pedagogy
of Primary Education of the Tashkent State Pedagogical
University named after Nizami
barotovamarjona30@gmail.com

Annotation. The article examines the theoretical and practical foundations for improving the methodology of developing information competence in future primary school teachers in the context of education digitalization. The importance of information competence as a key component of a teacher's professional training in the digital age is emphasized. The proposed methodology focuses on the integration of digital resources into the educational process, as well as the development of critical thinking, reflection, motivation, and pedagogical responsibility among students.

Keywords: information competence, education digitalization, future teachers, primary school, digital technologies, pedagogical methodology, student motivation, professional identity, reflection, digital pedagogy.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются теоретические и практические основы совершенствования методики развития информационной компетентности будущих учителей начальных классов в условиях цифровизации образования. Актуализируется значимость информационной компетентности как ключевого компонента профессиональной подготовки педагога в цифровую эпоху. Представлена методика, ориентированная на интеграцию цифровых ресурсов в учебный процесс, развитие критического мышления, рефлексии, мотивации и педагогической ответственности студентов.

Ключевые слова: информационная компетентность, цифровизация образования, будущие учителя, начальная школа, цифровые технологии, педагогическая методика, мотивация студентов, профессиональная идентичность, рефлексия, цифровая педагогика.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada raqamlashtirish sharoitida bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining axborot kompetentligini rivojlantirish metodikasini takomillashtirishning nazariy va amaliy asoslari ko'rib chiqiladi. Raqamli davrda pedagog kadrlarni tayyorlashda axborot kompetentligining asosiy tarkibiy qismlardan biri sifatida ahamiyati qayd etiladi. Ta'lim jarayoniga raqamli resurslarni integratsiya qilish, tanqidiy fikrlash, refleksiya, motivatsiya va talabalarning pedagogik mas'uliyatini rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan metodika taqdim etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot kompetentligi, ta'limni raqamlashtirish, bo'lajak o'qituvchilar, boshlang'ich sinf, raqamli texnologiyalar, pedagogik metodika, talabalar motivatsiyasi, kasbiy identiklik, refleksiya, raqamli pedagogika.

In modern conditions of digitalization, education is undergoing rapid changes associated with the widespread introduction of information and communication technologies (ICT) into all levels of the educational process. One of the key areas of reforming the teacher education system is the training of future teachers who are able to effectively use digital resources and technologies in their professional activities.

The information competence of future primary school teachers is of particular importance, since it is at the initial stage of schooling that the foundations of the information culture of students are laid. A teacher who knows modern ICT is able not only to transfer knowledge, but also to form the skills of searching, analyzing and critically evaluating information in younger students.

The problem lies in the fact that the current methods of teacher training are insufficiently focused on the development of information competence as an integral professional quality. In most cases, the acquisition of ICT is carried out in fragments and is not systematic, which reduces the effectiveness of preparing future teachers to work in a digital educational environment.

The need to improve the methodology of information competence development is also determined by the requirements of the professional standard of the teacher, in which information and communication competence is designated as one of the key ones. In addition, the digitalization of education requires teachers to be able to design, organize and support the educational process based on digital technologies, which is impossible without appropriate methodological training.

Modern research in the field of pedagogy and digital technologies emphasizes the importance of an integrated approach to the formation of information competence, including

both theoretical and practical training of students. However, there is a shortage of scientific literature devoted to the development and testing of techniques that ensure the integration of digital resources into the training of future teachers.

In modern conditions of digitalization, education is undergoing rapid changes associated with the widespread introduction of information and communication technologies (ICT) into all levels of the educational process. One of the key areas of reforming the teacher education system is the training of future teachers who are able to effectively use digital resources and technologies in their professional activities.

The information competence of future primary school teachers is of particular importance, since it is at the initial stage of schooling that the foundations of the information culture of students are laid. A teacher who knows modern ICT is able not only to transfer knowledge, but also to form the skills of searching, analyzing and critically evaluating information in younger students.

The problem lies in the fact that the current methods of teacher training are insufficiently focused on the development of information competence as an integral professional quality. In most cases, the acquisition of ICT is carried out in fragments and is not systematic, which reduces the effectiveness of preparing future teachers to work in a digital educational environment.

The need to improve the methodology of information competence development is also determined by the requirements of the professional standard of the teacher, in which information and communication competence is designated as one of the key ones. In addition, the digitalization of education requires teachers to be able to design, organize and support the educational process based on digital technologies, which is impossible without appropriate methodological training.

Modern research in the field of pedagogy and digital technologies emphasizes the importance of an integrated approach to the formation of information competence, including both theoretical and practical training of students. However, there is a shortage of scientific literature devoted to the development and testing of techniques that ensure the integration of digital resources into the training of future teachers.

There is an urgent need to create and implement methodological solutions aimed at developing the information competence of future primary school teachers in the context of digitalization of education. In this regard, the purpose of this study is to theoretically

substantiate and experimentally verify the methodology that contributes to the effective formation of this quality among students of pedagogical universities.

The theoretical and methodological basis of the research is based on the fundamental principles of competence-based, personality-oriented and activity-based approaches, as well as conceptual ideas of digital pedagogy, reflecting the peculiarities of the transformation of the educational process in the context of digitalization. The application of the competence approach has made it possible to consider information competence as a holistic integrative education, including interrelated cognitive, operational, and motivational-value components. This approach helped to determine the structure, content and mechanisms of information competence formation among future primary school teachers in accordance with the requirements of the modern educational environment.

The study was conducted on the basis of the pedagogical faculty of the university, which trains future primary school teachers. Two groups of third-year students served as an experimental base. In the control group, the educational process was based on traditional methods, while in the experimental group, the author's methodology was introduced, aimed at the purposeful development of information competence.

The methodology provided for the introduction of a modular course, including theoretical and practice-oriented components aimed at the formation and development of key competencies in the field of digital pedagogy for future teachers. The course content covered the development of modern digital tools, the design and testing of electronic educational resources, as well as the mastery of digital didactics technologies. Special attention was paid to solving professionally oriented tasks in a digital educational environment, which contributed to the formation of applied skills and professional thinking.

The diagnosis of the level of information competence formation was carried out on the basis of a developed system of criteria and indicators representing the degree of development of the key components of this competence. In particular, the level of the cognitive component was assessed, reflecting the degree of theoretical awareness in the field of information and communication technologies; the operational component, characterizing the formation of practical skills in using digital tools in professional activities.; as well as a motivational and value component, indicating the presence of a stable positive attitude and readiness to integrate ICT into teaching practice.

To quantify the level of information competence of future primary school teachers, a set of empirical methods was used, including questionnaires, testing, analysis of individual digital

portfolios of students, as well as an expert assessment of the quality of project assignments. Diagnostic procedures were performed at the ascertaining and final stages of the pedagogical experiment in order to identify the dynamics of changes in the control and experimental groups.

The analysis of empirical data was carried out using mathematical statistics methods. Statistical processing included calculating the arithmetic averages of indicators for each component of information competence (cognitive, operational, and motivational-value), determining the standard deviation (σ), and checking the statistical significance of differences between samples according to the Student's criterion for independent samples:

where:

x_1, x_2 are the average values for the experimental and control groups, respectively;

s_1^2, s_2^2 — group variances;

N_1, n_2 — the number of groups.

The obtained values of the Student's criterion were compared with tabular values with a significance level of $p < 0.05$ and a degree of freedom of $df = n_1 + n_2 - 2$. In the experimental group, there was a statistically significant increase in the average values for all components of information competence compared with the control group (for example, for the cognitive component: $x_1 = 4.32, x_2 = 3.68, t = 2.81, p < 0.01$), which confirms the effectiveness of the implemented methodology.

The results of the ascertaining stage of the pedagogical experiment demonstrated the absence of statistically significant differences in the level of information competence formation between students of the control and experimental groups at the initial stage of the study. Both samples were dominated by medium and low levels of cognitive, operational, and motivational-value components, which indicates that this competence was not sufficiently developed at the initial stage.

During the formative stage of the experiment, implemented through the introduction of the author's methodology, positive dynamics was recorded in the experimental group in all the parameters being diagnosed. The students demonstrated significantly better results when performing tasks aimed at applying information and communication technologies in their professional activities. An increase in the quality of project assignments was also noted, which indicates an increase in the operational component, and a steady display of interest and positive attitude towards digital educational technologies indicates a strengthening of the motivational and value component of information competence.

A qualitative analysis of the digital portfolios of the students of the experimental group revealed a quantitative and qualitative expansion of the arsenal of digital tools they use, increased creativity in designing and implementing their own electronic educational resources. The practical skills of working with modern educational platforms, interactive services and educational information visualization tools have significantly improved, which indicates the growth of functional literacy in the digital educational environment.

There was no significant positive dynamics in the control group: students continued to use a limited set of digital resources and demonstrated a low level of readiness for their pedagogical integration, which confirms the need for targeted methodological support for the formation of information competence.

The results of the statistical analysis performed using the Student's criterion confirmed the reliability of the differences between the control and experimental groups in all the studied indicators. The obtained values ($p < 0.05$) indicate the statistical significance of the identified differences, which substantiates the effectiveness and pedagogical effectiveness of the implemented author's methodology.

The results confirmed the hypothesis that the development of information competence requires targeted methodological support and integration of digital technologies into the educational process. The developed methodology allowed students not only to master specific digital tools, but also to realize the importance of information culture as a component of a teacher's professional skills.

A special feature of the proposed methodology is the combination of theoretical and practical training, orientation towards professionally significant activities and the active use of the digital environment as an educational and developmental space. This approach has contributed to the formation of a sustainable need for self-development and professional growth in the field of digital pedagogy.

Working with the motivational and value component of information competence turned out to be an important aspect. Through project and research activities, students realized the importance of digital technologies not only as a tool, but also as an environment that transforms educational reality and creates new forms of interaction with students.

The limitations of the study are related to the sample and duration of the experiment, which requires further verification of the methodology in a broader educational context and at other stages of professional training. It is also promising to deepen research towards the

personalization of digital learning and the development of digital competence development tracks.

The development of the digital educational environment places increasing demands on the information training of teachers. In this context, the improvement of the methodology of information competence formation is of strategic importance and should become an integral part of the modernization of teacher education.

Thus, in the course of the study, it was theoretically substantiated and experimentally confirmed that targeted methodological support contributes to the effective development of information competence of future primary school teachers. The implementation of the author's methodology has provided positive dynamics in all components of competence, which is confirmed by diagnostic results and statistical analysis.

The proposed approach can be recommended for use in the system of higher pedagogical education, as well as in the development of professional development programs for existing teachers. It opens up new opportunities for the formation of the digital culture of the future teacher, which is especially important in the context of intensive digitalization of the educational environment.

In the future, it is necessary to continue research aimed at improving digital educational modules that form the competencies of teachers in the context of continuous change and technological innovation. Information competence should be considered not only as a subject of formation, but also as a condition for the successful professional realization of a modern teacher.

List of used literature

1. Ахмедова Д.Ш. Замонавий таълимда ахборот-коммуникация технологиялари: методик ёндашувлар. – Тошкент: Фан ва технология, 2022. – 168 б.
2. Жононов О.А. Бошланғич таълимда рақамли компетенцияни шакллантириш асослари. – Самарқанд: Илм зиё, 2021. – 144 б.
3. Vaganova O.I., Smirnova Z.V. Formation of information competence of future teachers in the digital educational environment // Revista Inclusiones. – 2020. – Vol. 7(Special Edition). – P. 491–500.
4. Митрофанова Е.В. Развитие информационной компетентности педагога в условиях цифровой трансформации образования // Высшее образование в России. – 2020. – №3. – С. 120–127.

5. Selwyn N. Education and Technology: Key Issues and Debates. – London: Bloomsbury Academic, 2016. – 233 p.

6. Hakimov, F. N., & Ahmadova, G. N. (2025). THE CURRENT ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN BEGINNER CLASSES. SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM, 3(34), 95-98.

7. Barotova, M., & Quvvatova, D. (2019). Transference of national peculiarities in the novel "The Din" by E. A'zam. International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology, 8(5 Special Issue 3), 383-387.

8. Hayitov, A., & Xo'Shboqova, F. (2022). Integrativ yondashuv asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kommunikativ madaniyatni shakllantirish. Science and innovation, 1(B7), 1028-1034.

